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EVALUATION OF PRESCHOOL AND CLASSROOM TEACHERS' INSTRUCTIONAL ADAPTATIONS FOR INCLUSIVE STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This study aim; teachers' knowledge and attitudes towards teaching adaptations that facilitate the participation of children with special needs in inclusive education were tried to be evaluated. The study was designed according to the scanning model. Study data were collected using structured interview technique. In the study, 85 teachers participated. Five open-ended questions were asked to teachers to determine what kind of adaptations they made in the classroom. The interviews were conducted online by the researchers. As a result of the study, it was observed that the teachers did not have sufficient knowledge about children with special needs and they needed the necessary regulations and educational support for working with children with special needs.*

Key words: *inclusive student, special needs, teaching adaptations, preschool.*

Вступ

Introduction

Inclusive education is a special education practice where support services are provided, based on the principle of continuing education and training of individuals in need of special education together with their peers at all levels (MEB,2020). This definition shows us that each student has an individual characteristic and each of them has differences in terms of prior knowledge, interest, learning priorities, preferences and styles, socio-economic and development characteristics that they bring to the educational environment. For this reason, it is not realistic to expect these students with different characteristics to benefit at the same level from the uniform education offered to them. Students studying in the same class may differ in many ways, especially their auditory, visual and mental characteristics, and they cannot benefit from the teaching offered to them in the same way. Along with the large role of the mentioned student characteristics in the realization of the desired behavior change (learning), the features of the content to be taught in this process, the teaching methods used and the diversification of the teaching environment according to the different characteristics of the students are also important (Kılıc, 2013). The way to ensure that students benefit from teaching at the highest level is to diversify the teaching as much as possible, taking into account the different characteristics and needs of students (Belçer ve Avcı, 2011; Kontas, 2012; Aral, 2011). With the spread of inclusive education, it becomes compulsory to organize schools and classes to include all students and making adaptations that will meet the individual needs of the students (Rosenberg, Westling ve McLeskey, 2008). Instructional adaptations that include individualization of teaching are handled under different titles and, the main topics are; (a) Physical arrangements, (b) Regulations regarding the process, (c) Regulations regarding the classroom climate, (d) Instructional arrangements and (e) Regulations regarding the functioning (Smith, Polloway,

Patton ve Dowdy, 2008; Sandall, Schwartz, Gauvreau, 2016). In terms of equal opportunity in education, it is a very important issue in supporting the development of children that students with special needs receive education together with their peers with normal development by preparing the necessary infrastructure. In today's pandemic conditions, unfortunately, students have to take the majority of the education remotely (online) when getting face-to-face services. Therefore, teachers need to make adjustments in teaching in order to ensure that all students receive education under equal conditions. In this study, the knowledge and attitudes of teachers about teaching adaptations that facilitate the participation of children with special needs in inclusive education are evaluated.

Методи та методики дослідження *Methods and Techniques of the Research*

Research method: Action research, one of the qualitative research models, was used in the research. Action research: It involves practitioners studying the application process alone or with a researcher in order to understand and solve the problems that arise in practice (Büyüköztürk, 2016).

Study group: The study group of the research consists of 85 teachers, 43 women and 42 men. The average age of the participants is 22.6. In addition, 22 of the teachers are preschool teachers, 11 are classroom teachers and 5 are special education teachers. Considering their professional experience, 12 people have 10 years or more, 18 people have just started, and 55 people have 2 to 9 years of professional experience.

Data Collection and Analysis: Study data were collected using the structured interview technique. Five open-ended questions were asked to teachers to determine what kind of adaptations they made in the classroom (Questions; What are the arrangements made in the pre-teaching classroom, the arrangements made in the physical environment of the classroom, regulation of classroom climate, regulation of general functioning of the classroom and arrangements in classroom management?). The interviews were conducted online by the researchers. Each interview session lasted a minimum of 20 and a maximum of 35 minutes. The collected data were interpreted by the researchers and the comments were presented in the results section.

Результати *Results*

Findings regarding the opinions of the teachers at the end of the research are presented below according to the question headings.

1) What are the knowledge and opinions of the teachers about the arrangement of the pre-teaching classroom?

a) Regulation of the physical environment: Teachers said that they try to create an educational environment in line with the individual needs of the students, take care of not to use distracting objects and unnecessary details in the classroom, plan a special seating arrangement for group activities and individual events and try to create an environment in which children can feel comfortable and safe. Some teachers answered that they made an effort to create the least restrictive classroom environment.

b) In terms of classroom rules: Teachers stated that they set the rules together with the students in a way that is appropriate for their level so, it is easier for them to obey the rules. In addition, some teachers stated that they created boards to remind students of the

rules and that they visually support these boards for those who cannot read, and some teachers said that they created a personalized rule list and pasted a favorite emoji for each rule followed.

c) In terms of classroom climate: Some of the teachers stated that they took care to create environments where children could feel comfortable, approached their students lovingly, designed the classroom remarkably, removed dangerous materials out of reach of children, fixed lockers so that children would not harm themselves.

d) In terms of general functioning of the classroom: Teachers said that they made the lesson plans appropriately for the students, prepared the teaching activities according to the development level of the child, and sometimes talked about their favorite subject outside the lesson so that the children would not get bored. While some teachers, on the other hand, stated that they talked about the classroom rules with the interns, and they determined the deficiencies and needs of the class, Teachers who teach in an individual environment stated that it varies according to the student who comes to the lesson, for example, a student understands better visually, so their activities, rules and homework are given according to this issue.

e) Effective time and homework: Teachers stated that they came prepared to classroom in advance for the effective use of time and keep the materials and equipment which they will use during the lesson ready. For homework, they stated that they gave homework according to the skill or subject studied in the lesson and informed the family about the homework.

When the distribution of the responses given by the teachers is examined according to the regulations regarding the teaching process and the dimensions of the physical arrangements, it is seen that teachers stated that adaptation in physical arrangements are more needed to be made in inclusive education than the regulations regarding the teaching process. This finding is also consistent with the literature. In the literature, it is stated that physical arrangements are the first to come to mind in inclusive education and are frequently made arrangements (Choate, 2000; Friend ve Bursuck, 2002; Lewis ve Doorlag, 1999).

2) What are the teachers' opinions about the arrangements made in the physical environment of the classroom?

a) General physical structure of the environment (temperature of the classroom, amount of light, etc.): Some teachers said that subjects such as heat and light are determined by the administration. Some teachers stated that they take additional precautions for their students who are sensitive to sound and light. For example, a teacher stated that she frequently warned her students to be helpful to her sound sensitive student in her classroom and even supported this warning with visuals at the beginning.

b) Arrangement of equipment (items in the classroom): The teachers stated that the tables and benches were suitable for the height of the children, they removed the hazardous materials where they could not reach, and that the tools such as lockers were fixed. They stated that they do not allow materials that could distract children, in items. Teachers stated that they made some materials suitable for online environment in online education in order to make learning process easier and effective.

c) Accessibility: Teachers did not answer this question at first and answered after the concept of accessibility was explained. The answers given by teachers are generally that there is a disability ramp in their schools. Some of the teachers think that the work done for accessibility is insufficient. Also, some of the teachers thought that there was a sensible

walking surface in their schools, and that this made the situation of the students even more difficult because it was not done correctly.

Arrangements in the physical environment of the classroom cover changes in social, physical environment and temporary situations in order to support children's participation in the learning process and engagement in activities. First of all, arranging the classroom environment in a way that all children can access can be considered as a prerequisite for learning processes to happen (Horn, Kang, Classen, & Lieber, 2016). It is seen that the teachers participating in the study also have a similar opinion about the physical arrangement of the classrooms.

3) *What kind of work do you do to regulate the classroom climate (Creating a positive classroom climate and a general acceptance atmosphere for students with special needs and for all students in the classroom)?*

Common responses given by the teachers; Teachers said that they try to give the students team spirit via group activities in order to create the general acceptance atmosphere in the classroom, they do not discriminate their students and they do awareness activities. For example, the teacher who working in practice school said that he does an awareness study for a student's disability every week. One of the teachers in this question said: *“I try to create a more comfortable atmosphere for students with low self-esteem. I try to help them to understand that they can also give the wrong answer while encouraging them to ask questions. In group lessons, I try to create an environment where they can interact with each other more, see each other's differences and feel more comfortable.”*

Levy (2008) suggested in his study that the instructions given to the student to complete the activity could be simplified. Also, he added that an alternative curriculum can be created in line with the needs of students. In the interviews, it is seen that the teachers emphasized knowing the students well. In addition, teachers stated that they can contribute to the learning process of students and increase their participation in classroom activities by responding positively to the small progress and efforts made by students.

4) *What kind of work do teachers do to regulate the general functioning of the classroom?*

Teachers' answers to this question are similar to each other. Common answers; Works on the regulation of the general functioning of the classroom made by teachers cover everything in class functioning such as Starting and ending the lesson on time, making and applying a lesson plan, controlling the light and heat level of the classroom at the beginning of the lesson, Removing materials that were used in the previous lesson but not needed in that lesson, using materials in a way that gives the student a clue about the subject to be covered and placing them where the student can see. Some of the teachers stated that they try to establish rules that will enable students to learn effectively and adapt to social life easily. However, They stated that they needed serious support in this process, but they could not always get the necessary support from the management. Carolan and Guinn (2007) stated that differentiated teaching requires teachers to spend a lot of time and, teachers need professional development resources and administrative support, but they do not have this support sufficiently.

5) *What kind of works do teachers do in order to “use time effectively” in classroom management?*

To this question, most of the teachers stated that it is necessary to make a lesson plan in order to use time effectively. Also, they added that the steps in the lesson plan for effective time management should be planned and implemented according to the needs of the student. In this subject, one of the teacher said: *“It is very important to use all the time*

of the lessons in the most efficient way and there are various ways to achieve this. Most students can get bored too much, students with high level disabilities can be. First of all, as I said, the most important thing is to get to know each student. There should always be a backup plan that will ensure the effective participation of the student in the lesson, and I use them as reinforcers in the teaching I want to do. I always try to be close with the student and gain their attention. If education is disrupted in special education, students may experience a decline. Thus, it is necessary not to miss the education even in one lesson and it is necessary to use all the time. So, I try to keep the education functioning considering the student wants in order to use time effectively and fully.” However, Generally, teachers stated that the classes were crowded and therefore they could not devote enough time to students. Also, teachers stated that they had to shorten the time in the case of distance education.

Considering the results, it was seen that many regulations in two groups, which are important for students with special needs, were not considered important enough by their teachers. As the main reason for this situation, it can be accepted that teachers have limited knowledge about Support to be provided to students with special needs who are studying in inclusive classrooms, Arrangements to be made within the scope of special education services and provision of these to students (Kargın, Gu İdenog lu & S ahin, 2010).

Висновки **Conclusions**

Teachers who works in inclusive education need to know that schools and primarily classrooms should be organized in a way to meet different student needs in order to students with special needs receive education with their peers in inclusive environments. It is also very important for teachers to be able to define student needs and make adaptations in the curriculum, teaching objectives, teaching methods and tools to meet these requirements. As a result of the study, it was observed that the teachers did not have sufficient knowledge about children with special needs and they needed the necessary regulations and educational support for children with special needs. Therefore, courses on children with special needs and arrangements to facilitate the learning of these children, can be organized for all teachers who will work with special needs children. This research is a qualitative study and is limited to the information obtained only from the interviews. In the future, this subject can be done with experimental applications using the quantitative research method.

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